

Liste de références – Affiche EPK 785

- Barnett, L. M., van Beurden, E., Morgan, P. J., Brooks, L. O. et Beard, J. R. (2009). Childhood motor skill proficiency as a predictor of adolescent physical activity. *Journal of Adolescent Health, 44*(3), 252-259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2008.07.004>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), Brener, N. D., Kann, L., Shanklin, S., Kinchen, S., Eaton, D. K., Hawkins, J. et Flint, K. H. (2013). Methodology of the youth risk behavior surveillance system--2013. *MMWR. Recommendations and Reports: Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report. Recommendations and Reports, 62*(RR-1), 1-20.
- Groupe de recherche sur les saines habitudes de vie et l'obésité. (2017). *Évaluation canadienne de la littératie physique - Manuel d'instructions - Deuxième édition*. <https://www.activehealthykids.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/capl-2-manual-fr.pdf>
- International physical literacy association. (2017). Physical activity for LIFE. <https://www.physical-literacy.org.uk/about/>
- Larouche, R., Boyer, C., Tremblay, M. S. et Longmuir, P. (2014). Physical fitness, motor skill, and physical activity relationships in grade 4 to 6 children. *Applied Physiology, Nutrition, and Metabolism, 39*(5), 553-559. <https://doi.org/10.1139/apnm-2013-0371>
- Lopes, V., Rodrigues, L., Maia, J. et Malina, R. (2011). Motor coordination as predictor of physical activity in childhood. *Scand J Med Sci Sports, 21*(5), 663-669. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0838.2009.01027.x>
- Morrow, J. R., Tucker, J. S., Jackson, A. W., Martin, S. B., Greenleaf, C. A. et Petrie, T. A. (2013). Meeting physical activity guidelines and health-related fitness in youth. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine, 44*(5), 439-444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2013.01.008>
- Okely, A., Booth, M. et Patterson, J. (2001). Relationship of physical activity to fundamental movement skills among adolescents. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise, 33*(11), 1899-1904.
- Société canadienne de physiologie de l'exercice. (s. d.). *Directives canadiennes en matière de mouvement sur 24 heures pour les enfants et les jeunes (5 à 17 ans)*. <https://directivesscpe.ca/directives/enfants-et-jeunes-2/>